

Unemployment, Inflation and Economic Growth in Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

This study examined the impacts of unemployment and inflation rates on economic growth in Nigeria within the period 1981-2020. Data for the study were obtained from the Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics and the variables of interest (Real gross domestic product growth rate, Unemployment rate, Inflation rate, Gross fixed capital formation growth rate) were analysed using the autoregressive distributed lag model because the unit root test results from the Augmented Dickey-Fuller and the Phillipps-Perron tests indicated that the variables of the study have mixed orders of integration, namely zero and one. The study found that a 1% increase in unemployment rate translates into -0.17% and -0.29% decline in real GDP growth in the short and long runs respectively, whereas for inflation rate, the decline are -0.1% and -0.25% for the short run and long run respectively. The study therefore concluded that rising unemployment causes more harm to the economy than the inflation rate. The study recommends that the federal government of Nigeria should see the problem of unemployment as a serious than one and tackle it headlong by designing and implementing new policies and programmes that target the reduction of the national unemployment rate by a certain proportion within a stipulated time. The Nigerian Government should also strengthen the use of institutional approach to control inflation and aim at returning to single-digit inflation rate to reduce its adverse effect on the economy.

Keywords: Unemployment Rate, Inflation Rate, Real GDP, ARDL, Bounds Test

1. INTRODUCTION

Inflation and unemployment are two factors that significantly affect an economy's ability to thrive. Each nation faces the difficulty of bringing these two factors down to a manageable level, although some have had more difficulty than others. Nigeria is classified as a lower-middle-income country. However, this hasn't always been the situation. The Nigerian economy remained comparatively stable in the first ten years after the country gained its independence. The majority of Nigerians had employment, and the country's economy even welcomed a sizable influx of foreign workers while maintaining comparatively low rates of inflation. There was relative industrial harmony and the wages compared favorably to worldwide norms (Miftahu, 2021). However, the Nigerian economic structure was severely distorted by the oil boom of the early 1970s. This led to mass migration of young people to cities in pursuit of gainful employment. Regrettably, the issue of unemployment was aggravated by the economic crisis that occurred in the early 1980s. Since the economy was growing more and more dependent on imports, inflation also started to increase.

For this reason, the patterns of Nigeria's inflation, unemployment, and economic growth rates throughout time have proven perplexing. According to historical statistics from the CBN (2020) and NBS (2020), Nigeria's overall unemployment rate climbed from 5.2% in 1981 to 18.1% in 2000. It was 21.4% by 2010, and by 2020 it had reached 33.3% (CBN, 2020). Comparably, the consumer price index showed a 20.8% inflation rate in 1978 but just a 5.4% inflation rate in 2007. That did, however, average 13.8% year between 2016 and 2020. The lowest rates of inflation and unemployment during the 1981–2020 study period were 5.4% in 2007 and 2% in 1994, respectively. However, in the middle of an economic crisis that saw the Nigerian

economy contract by -1.92% in 2020 over the previous year, the unemployment rate reached 33.3% at the end of 2020 and the inflation rate lingered around 13.25% at the same time (NBS, 2020; CBN, 2020).

In an attempt to address Nigeria's unemployment issue, the government began relying more on entrepreneurial initiatives and programs for skill development and empowerment (such the N-Power program) when the Small and Medium Scale Enterprises Development Agency was established in 2001. Similarly, in order to maintain low inflation rates in the economy, the CBN has frequently favored contractionary monetary policy positions over expansionary ones. Despite these efforts, the jobless rate skyrocketed to 33.33% in 2020, the inflation rate has been in the double digits since 2016, and the economy grew at a lackluster 0.3% annual average pace between 2016 and 2020.

Owing to Nigeria's challenges in controlling inflation and unemployment, achieving and sustaining a stable economy marked by manageable rates of both have become key policy concerns. This is also known as full employment and price stability. The current study was motivated by the persistence of unemployment and inflation in the Nigerian economy. It aimed to reexamine the impact of these two issues on economic growth in Nigeria, with a particular focus on the years 1981–2020. The goal was to propose evidence-based policy actions that could contribute to the desired outcome of repositioning Nigeria as a stable and equitable economy. The rest of the paper is organized as follows: section 2 dwelt of literature review, section 3 focused on methodology, section 4 presents the result while section 5 concludes the paper.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Theoretical and empirical review

Classical versus Keynesian theories of unemployment

Classical economics refers to a school of thought in economics popularized from the late 18th to the early-to-mid 19th centuries, mainly in Britain. The main adherents of the school are thought to be Adam Smith, Jean-Baptiste Say, David Ricardo, Thomas Robert Malthus, and John Stuart Mill. These economists produced a theory of market economies as largely self-regulating systems, governed by natural laws of production and exchange (Samuelson, 1978). The fundamental principle of the classical theory is that the economy is self-regulating. The classicists assume the existence of full employment without inflation. Given wage-price flexibility, there are automatic forces in the economic system that tend to maintain full employment and produce output at that level (Samuelson, 1978). In the classical model, equilibrium income and employment are determined largely in the labor market. At lower wage rates, more workers will be employed. That is why the demand curve of labor is downward sloping.

The classicists also hold that there is always full employment, so the existence of unemployed workers is a logical impossibility. Any unemployment that existed at the equilibrium wage rate was due to frictions or restrictive practices in the economy. Thus, full employment is regarded by the classicists as a normal situation, while unemployment is abnormal. However, these views were vehemently opposed by John Maynard Keynes as economies began to fail in the early 20th century. Keynes taught that the economy could settle in equilibrium at any level of unemployment. This meant that classical policies of non-intervention (automatic adjustment) would not work.

In his theory, Keynes (1936) states that employment depends on effective demand; effective demand results in output; output creates income; and income provides employment. Thus, he regards employment as a function of income. Also, effective demand depends on the aggregate supply and demand function. Since Keynes assumed that aggregate supply was stable, he concentrated on aggregate demand to fight depression and unemployment. According to him, employment can be increased by increasing consumption and/or investment. Consumption depends on income, and when income rises, consumption also rises but not as much as income. The Keynesian framework, as examined by Thirlwall (1979), Grill and Zanalda (1995), and Hussain and Nadol (1997), postulates that an increase in employment, capital stock, and technological change are largely endogenous. Thus the growth of employment is demand-determined and the fundamental determinants of long-term growth of output also influence the growth of employment. Another basic principle of Keynesian economics is that government spending is necessary to maintain full employment, even if a government has to go into debt. This, however, has paved the way for criticizing Keynesian economics as critics are of the view that the Keynesian theory is deficient because Keynes' stance promotes deficit spending, stifles private investment, and causes inflation (Aminu, Manu, & Salihu, 2013). Nevertheless, the theory is widely acclaimed over the classical approach, and therein lays its relevance to the present study.

The empirical literature on the impact of unemployment, inflation, and economic growth in Nigeria reveals diverse findings and methodological considerations.

Starting with the studies on the impact of unemployment on economic growth, several researchers have examined this relationship using various econometric methods. For instance, Miftahu (2021) utilized the Ordinary Least Squares (OLS) method and found a significant negative effect of unemployment on GDP, although concerns were raised about the methodology's robustness. Similarly, Ajie, Aniekan, and Ameh (2018) employed OLS and concluded that unemployment did not significantly impact economic growth, but the study's model complexity and failure to account for different orders of integration in variables were noted drawbacks. Contrarily, Eze, Atuma, and Egbeoma (2016) employed a cointegration and Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and found a significant negative impact of unemployment on real GDP, offering insights into the long-term relationship between the variables.

Concerning studies on the impact of inflation on economic growth, researchers like Miftahu (2021) observed a significant positive effect of inflation on GDP, contrary to economic theory. This finding, however, was questioned due to methodological issues. Similarly, Ajie, Aniekan, and Ameh (2018) found no significant impact of inflation on economic growth using OLS, but limitations in methodology were highlighted. Ademola and Badiru (2016) utilized cointegration and ECM and found a significant negative effect of inflation on short-run GDP growth, suggesting the importance of considering both short-term and long-term dynamics in analyzing this relationship.

Overall, while empirical studies offer valuable insights into the relationships between unemployment, inflation, and economic growth in Nigeria, methodological considerations such as appropriate model selection, testing for long-run relationships, and addressing data limitations are crucial for robust and reliable findings. Further research using advanced econometric techniques and comprehensive data analysis could provide deeper insights into these complex dynamics.

3. Methodology

Research design

This study is based on the ex post facto research design. Ex post facto study or after-the-fact research is a category of research design in which the investigation starts after the fact has occurred without interference from the researcher. This design is appropriate for examining cause-and-effect relationships among economic variables, the process of which cannot be manipulated by the researcher (Salkind, 2010).

Data Sources

The empirical model of this study has four variables: real GDP growth rate, unemployment rate, inflation rate, and gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) growth rate. The growth rates of real GDP and GFCF were computed using Excel spread sheet as follows: [(current year value – previous year value) ÷ previous year value × 100]. The values are in per cent (%). No transformations were made to the data on unemployment and inflation rates as they are used in their original forms. While economic growth, unemployment rate, and inflation rate have been previously defined in this study, gross fixed capital formation (GFCF) measures the value of net additions to fixed assets, excluding all kinds of financial assets as well as stocks of inventories and other operating costs. As such, GFCF is not a measure of total investment (OECD, 2013). The data for this study were obtained from secondary sources. The real GDP, inflation rate, and gross fixed capital formation were obtained from the 2020 Central Bank of Nigeria Statistical Bulletin.

Model specification

This study estimated a growth function of the Cobb-Douglas kind,

$$Y = AL^{\beta}K^{\alpha} \quad 1$$

where the main factors that account to increase in output are labour stock (L), capital stock (K), and aspects of technological progress (A). To domesticate the model in this study, we adopted the Okun-type model (Okun, 1962) where change in real GDP is explained by change in unemployment rate (proxy labour stock). However, the present study modified the reference model by incorporating inflation rate as in Miftahu (2021), Ademola and Badiru (2016), Onwachukwu (2015), and Sa'idu and Muhammad (2015). Further modification was done by incorporating a variable from the endogenous growth model, namely gross fixed capital formation. Assuming that the rate of growth of GDP is linearly related with unemployment rate, inflation rate, and rate of growth of gross fixed capital formation, the model of the study is specified as,

$$RGDPgr = f(UNR, INF, GFCFgr) \quad 2$$

Where,

RGDPgr = Real gross domestic product growth rate

UNR = Unemployment rate (proxy labour stock)

INF = Inflation rate (annual percentage change in consumer price index)

GFCFgr = Gross fixed capital formation growth rate (proxy capital stock)

The explicit form of the model is as follows,

$$RGDP_{gr} = \beta_0 + \beta_1 UNR + \beta_2 INF + \beta_3 GFCF_{gr} + \mu_t$$

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Where,

β_0 = the intercept of the regression line (or the constant term),

and β_1 , β_2 , and β_3 = parameters of the independent variables.

The a priori expectations are as follows:

$\beta_0 > 0$, $\beta_1 < 0$, $\beta_2 < 0$, and $\beta_3 > 0$ (i.e. β_0 , & β_3 are non-negative values while β_1 , & β_2 are negative values).

Estimation procedure

To estimate equation 2, the stability properties of the variables employed were first investigated by means of stationarity tests. Two unit-root tests were used in the study: the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF), and the Phillips-Perron (PP). The choice of two unit-root tests was informed by the imperatives of comparison and consistency. According to Hamilton (1994), the PP unit root test is generally considered to have a greater reliability than the ADF counterpart because it presents lower chances of serial correlation and heteroscedasticity problems, though it has its own shortcomings. The unit root test results revealed the orders of integrations of the variables which in turn determined what method of estimation is most suitable for the model.

4. RESULTS AND INTERPRETATION

Preliminary results

Descriptive statistics of the study variables

Table 1: Descriptive statistics

Variable	RGDPGR	UNR	INF	GFCFGR
Mean	3.795500	13.33800	18.97375	-0.506000
Median	4.130000	12.25000	12.55000	0.950000
Maximum	14.60000	33.30000	72.80000	40.39000
Minimum	-13.13000	2.000000	5.400000	-30.17000
Std. Dev.	5.109803	9.120294	16.87830	13.43429
Skewness	-0.835234	0.501590	1.822964	0.150681
Kurtosis	4.858924	1.931832	5.152491	4.011452
Jarque-Bera	10.41010	3.578921	29.87667	1.856423
Probability	0.005489	0.167050	0.000000	0.395260
Sum	151.8200	533.5200	758.9500	-20.24000
Sum Sq. Dev.	1018.293	3244.010	11110.20	7038.722
Observations	40	40	40	40

The result in Table 1 shows the descriptive statistics of the study data. Real GDP growth rate (RGDPGR) averaged 3.8% within the period under review (1981-2020), with maximum of 14.6% in 2002 and minimum of -13.13% in 1981. Similarly, unemployment rate averaged 13.3% in the period with the peak of 33.3% in 2020 and the smallest value of 2% in 1994. Inflation rate averaged 19.0% in the period with the highest rate of 72.8% in 1995 and the lowest 5.4% in 2007. Then gross fixed capital formation growth rate averaged -0.51% over the period and ranged between -30.17% in 1984 and 40.39% in 2006. RGDPGR has the smallest

standard deviation (5.1) implying that this variable has the most convergence compared to the other three. The probability of the Jaque-Bera statistic shows that unemployment rate (UNR) and Gross fixed capital formation growth rate (GFCFGR) are normally distributed as they are the ones greater than 0.05, whereas RGDPGR and inflation rate (INF) are not.

Unit root test results

The unit root test was performed both with the Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) method and then with the Phillips-Perron method. Summary of the results are presented in Tables 2 and 3.

Table 2: ADF unit root test result

Variable	ADF Test Statistic @ Level	5% critical value	P-value	ADF Test Statistic @ 1 st Difference	5% critical value	P-value	Order of Integration
RGDPGR	-4.433	-2.939	0.001	-	-	-	I(0)
UNR	-0.152	-2.939	0.936	-5.585	-2.941	0.000	I(1)
INF	-2.955	-2.939	0.048	-	-	-	I(1)
GFCFGR	-4.917	-2.941	0.000	-	-	-	I(0)

The result in Table 2 shows that the variables have mixed orders of integration. Some (RGDPGR & GFCFGR) are integrated of order zero while the others (UNR & INF) are integrated of order one according to the ADF method. However, we employed the Phillips-Perron test to confirm the results from the ADF method in order to be really sure about the stationarity of the data.

Table 3: Summary of Phillips-Perron (PP) unit root test result

Variable	Phillips-Perron Test Statistic @ Level	5% critical value	P-value	Phillips-Perron Test Statistic @ 1 st Difference	5% critical value	P-value	Order of Integration
RGDPGR	-4.4338	-2.9389	0.0011	-	-	-	I(0)
UNR	0.4015	-2.9389	0.9805	-5.7187	-2.9411	0.000	I(1)
INF	-2.8246	-2.9389	0.0641	-10.0227	-2.9411	0.000	I(1)
GFCFGR	-5.7183	-2.9389	0.000	-	-	-	I(0)

As presented in Table 3, the Phillips-Perron unit root test method confirms the earlier results from the ADF method that RGDPGR and GFCFGR are stationary at level whereas the other two, UNR and INF, are stationary at first difference. Based on the mixed orders of integration – at level and at first difference – the researcher estimated the autoregressive distributed lag (ARDL) model.

Results of model analysis**ARDL Short-run result****Table 4: Short-run result (Dependent variable: RGDPGR)**

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
RGDPGR(-1)	0.405477	0.140948	2.876772	0.0075
UNR	-0.173279	0.073127	-2.369559	0.0247
INF	-0.100431	0.042911	-2.340467	0.0263
INF(-1)	0.081187	0.057712	1.406777	0.1701
INF(-2)	-0.059370	0.055503	-1.069663	0.2936
INF(-3)	-0.072291	0.042945	-1.683345	0.1030
GFCFGR	0.015068	0.043271	0.348235	0.7302
CointEq(-1)	-0.594523	0.140948	-4.218018	0.0002
C	8.175004	2.196591	3.721678	0.0008
R-squared	0.502750	Mean dependent var	4.711081	
Adjusted R-squared	0.382725	S.D. dependent var	3.874116	
S.E. of regression	3.043772	Akaike info criterion	5.252883	
Sum squared resid	268.6719	Schwarz criterion	5.601189	
Log likelihood	-89.17833	Hannan-Quinn criter.	5.375677	
F-statistic	4.188686	Durbin-Watson stat	2.289840	
Prob(F-statistic)	0.002680			

Judging from the p-values of the results in Table 4, we can conclude that in the short run:

- i. Current unemployment rate (UNR) has significant negative impact on real GDP growth such that 1% rise in UNR is associated with -0.173% decline in GDP growth.
- i. Current inflation rate (INF) has significant negative impact on GDP growth such that 1% rise in INF results in -0.1% decline in real GDP growth;
- i. The first, second, and third lags of INF do not have significant impact on real GDP growth;
- i. Gross Fixed Capital Formation growth rate (GFCFGR) has positive sign as expected but no significant impact on real GDP growth in the short run.
- i. Lastly, the short-run model has speed of adjustment of 59% per annum which means convergence towards long-run equilibrium within two years following disequilibrium.

ARDL Bounds Test result

The study tested for long-run relationship among the variables used in the study using the ARDL Bounds Test. The result obtained is as follows.

Table 5: Result of ARDL Bounds Test

Null Hypothesis: No long-run relationships exist

Test Statistic	Value	K
F-statistic	4.583776	3

Critical Value Bounds

Significance	I0 Bound	I1 Bound
10%	2.72	3.77
5%	3.23	4.35
2.5%	3.69	4.89
1%	4.29	5.61

As indicated in Table 5, the F-statistic value of 4.58 is greater than the upper Bound value of 4.35 at 5% level of significance. This is the necessary condition for rejecting the null hypothesis that 'No long-run relationships exist'. We therefore conclude that long-run relationships exist among the study variables.

Long-run results

Table 6: Long-run result (Dependent variable: RGDPGR)

Long Run Coefficients				
Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.
UNR	-0.291459	0.131531	-2.215900	0.0347
INF	-0.253824	0.094639	-2.682021	0.0120
GFCFGR	0.025345	0.070860	0.357684	0.7232
C	13.750518	3.491479	3.938308	0.0005

The result in Table 6 shows that in the long run UNR and INF have significant negative impacts, while GFCFGR has no significant impact, on real GDP growth in Nigeria. Specifically, 1% rises in UNR and INF are associated with -0.29% and -0.25% losses in real GDP growth respectively.

Model diagnostics

Figure 1: Histogram normality test result

In Figure 1, the p-value is used to test the null hypothesis that the residuals are normally distributed against the alternative that they are not. The p-value of 0.837 is greater than 0.05, which means that the null hypothesis is accepted at the 5% level of significance. This implies

that the regression residuals are normally distributed as expected. This satisfies one of the underlying assumptions of the traditional regression model.

Autocorrelation/Serial correlation test results

Table 7: Breusch-Godfrey Serial Correlation LM Test:

F-statistic	0.623777	Prob. F(3,26)	0.6060
Obs*R-squared	2.484247	Prob. Chi-Square(3)	0.4781

Source: Researcher's own computations from EViews 9, 2024

The result in Table 7 shows that the p-values of the F-statistic and the Chi-Square statistic are each greater than 0.05, which implies acceptance of the null hypothesis of no autocorrelation in the estimated model. Again, this satisfies another important assumption of the classical regression model.

Heteroskedasticity test result

Table 8: Result of heteroskedasticity test: Breusch-Pagan-Godfrey

F-statistic	0.420620	Prob. F(7,29)	0.8814
Obs*R-squared	3.410328	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.8446
Scaled explained SS	1.868868	Prob. Chi-Square(7)	0.9667

In Table 8, the F-statistic and the Chi-Square statistic are used to test for the presence or absence of heteroscedasticity (non-constant variance of the regression residuals). The null hypothesis being tested is that of 'No heteroscedasticity in the estimated model'. As shown in the Table, the p-values of the statistics are all greater than 0.05 which implies that the null hypothesis of homoscedasticity is accepted. Thus the assumption of constant variance is not violated.

5 DISCUSSION AND HYPOTHESIS TESTING

Test of Research Hypothesis

Hypothesis One

H_0 : Unemployment rate has no significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

H_1 : Unemployment rate has significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

Decision rule: Reject H_0 if the p-value of the estimated t-Statistic of the unemployment rate (UNR) variable is less than 0.05; otherwise do not reject H_0 .

Result and conclusion: The ARDL result in Table 5 shows that short-run regression coefficient of current unemployment rate (UNR) is -0.173 with T-statistic -2.37 and p-value 0.0247. Likewise the long-run coefficient of the variable is -0.29 with T-statistic of -2.22 and p-value of 0.0347. The p-values are clearly less than 0.05, so we have enough evidence to reject the null hypothesis and it stands rejected. We therefore conclude that unemployment rate has significant negative impact on Nigeria's economic growth in the short and long runs.

Hypothesis Two

H_0 : Inflation rate has no significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

H_1 : Inflation rate has significant impact on Nigeria's economic growth.

Decision rule: Reject H_0 if the p-value of the estimated T-statistic of the inflation rate (INF) variable is less than 0.05; otherwise, do not reject H_0 .

Result and conclusion: The ARDL result in Table 5 shows that the short-run coefficient of inflation rate is -0.1 with T-statistic equal to -2.34 and p-value equal to 0.026. Similarly, the long-run coefficient of the variable is -0.254 with T-statistic equal to -2.68 and p-value 0.01. Again, the p-value is clearly less than 0.05, so we have strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis and it stands rejected. We can therefore conclude that inflation rate has significant negative impact on Nigeria's economic growth both in the short run and in the long run.

Unemployment rate and Growth of Real GDP in Nigeria

The study found that unemployment rate (UNR) had significant negative impact on real GDP growth in Nigeria. Specifically, it was found that in the short run 1% rise in unemployment rate is associated with -0.17% decline in real GDP growth while in the long run the decline stretches to -2.9%. Unemployment represents idle manpower or unused resources. It is like the labour component of the traditional production function which combines with capital and technological progress to produce goods. Hence this study rightly points out that the more the human resource resources stockpiles the more damaging to the economy in the form of loss of output.

The finding of this study regarding the negative impact of unemployment rate on economic growth is in tandem with those of previous studies in Nigeria by Miftahu (2021), and Eze, Atuma, and Egbeoma (2016). However, it differs from those of Ajie, Aniekan, and Ameh (2017), Onwachukwu (2015), and Sa'idu and Muhammad (2015) who found no significant impact of the variable, and that of Ademola and Badiru (2016) which reported positive impact of the variable.

Inflation rate and Growth of Real GDP in Nigeria

The study found that inflation rate has significant negative impact on growth of real GDP in Nigeria whether in the short run or in the long run. The empirical results of the study show that 1% rise in inflation rate results in -0.1% decline in real GDP growth in the short run while it rises to -0.25% in the long-run. The results highlight the detrimental effects of inflation rate in Nigeria and that it worsens as the years go by. Inflation rate as used in this study refers to percentage change in consumer price index. The index measures the percentage change in the prices of selected consumer or household goods in a given year compared to same point in time in the previous year.

This finding agrees with those of the study by Ademola and Badiru (2016) and Onwachukwu (2015) who reported significant negative impact of inflation on economic growth; whereas it is not in agreement with those of Ajie, Aniekan, and Ameh (2017) who found no significant impact of the variable, and Miftahu (2021), and Sa'idu and Muhammad (2015) who reported that inflation has positive impact on the real GDP, a result that is clearly arguable.

Conclusion and recommendation

This study examined the impacts of unemployment and inflation rates on economic growth in Nigeria within the period 1981-2020. Data for the study were obtained from Central Bank of Nigeria statistical bulletin and National Bureau of Statistics and analysed using autoregressive distributed lag model. The study finds that 1% rise in unemployment rate translates into -0.17% and -0.29% losses in real GDP growth in the short and long runs respectively, whereas for inflation rate the losses are -0.1% and -0.25% for short run and long run respectively. The

study therefore concludes that rising unemployment causes more harm to the economy than inflation rate. Overall though, the implication of the results is that no meaningful growth can be achieved in the Nigerian economy in the presence of soaring unemployment and inflation rates.

1. The federal government of Nigeria should see the problem of unemployment as more serious than inflation and tackle it headlong by designing and implementing new policies and programmes that target the reduction of national unemployment rate by a certain proportion within a stipulated time period.
2. The Nigeria government should strengthen the use of institutional approach to control inflation and aim at a returning to single-digit inflation rate to reduce its adverse effect on the economy.

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